

On the Impossibility of Lossless Waveform Rank Reduction for Certain Redundant Arrays

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Abstract—Efficient use of spatio-temporal resources, including sensor arrays and transmit waveforms, is a key challenge in modern MIMO active sensing systems. This paper studies the impact of array redundancy and waveform rank (WR) on active sensing performance. Specifically, we show that parameter identifiability at *reduced* WR critically depends on subspace properties of the so-called array redundancy pattern. We show that array geometries with identical sum co-arrays can exhibit markedly different identifiability properties at low WR. We derive a novel necessary condition for maximizing identifiability at reduced WR, which reveals that the unfavorable redundancy patterns of certain redundant arrays fundamentally limits their performance. The results yield new insights into resource-efficient sensing systems, motivating redundancy-aware array and waveform design.

Index Terms—Active sensing, array redundancy, identifiability, MIMO, sparse arrays, sum co-array, waveform design.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) active sensing systems, such as MIMO radars, leverage the ability of transmitters to launch independent *waveforms* to improve sensing performance, including target identifiability and resolution. Such MIMO waveforms can be represented by a $T \times N_t$ matrix \mathbf{S} , where N_t denotes the number of transmit (Tx) sensors and T is the waveform length (in samples). It is well-known that *full-rank waveforms* ($\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) = N_t$), such as orthogonal waveforms, reap the full diversity benefits provided by the N_t transmitters [1]. However, *reduced-rank* waveforms ($\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t$) also have several advantages, such as improved transmit beamforming gain and resulting parameter estimation performance [2], [3], and a need for fewer costly radio-frequency (RF) chains. Low-dimensional Tx signals also naturally arise in modern MIMO communications systems employing an excess of base station antennas compared to the number of user devices [4]. With the emergence of integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) [5]–[8], reduced waveform rank (WR) is thereby increasingly relevant also in sensing. This begs the questions: *Can WR be reduced without giving up the performance of full WR? What enables or prevents doing this?*

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To answer these questions, we will shed new light on the *sum co-array* [9]—a ubiquitous virtual array model in active sensing, known to govern sensing performance at full WR. Specifically, we will show that when operating at reduced WR, *not all MIMO arrays with the same co-array are created equal*. Indeed, there exists array geometries for which reducing WR leads to an inevitable loss of performance, such as fewer identifiable targets. Our focus is on *redundant* array geometries, which have repeated virtual sensors—in contrast to nonredundant arrays typically considered in MIMO radar. Redundant arrays, such as uniform linear arrays (ULAs), are key in a multitude of applications prioritizing, e.g., beamforming capability [3], [6], [10] and robustness to sensor failure [11]. An important and insofar largely neglected attribute of the array geometry is the so-called *redundancy pattern* (defined in Section III), which provides a mapping between the *physical* Tx and receive (Rx) sensors and the *virtual* sensors of the co-array. As we will see, the redundancy pattern plays a key role in reducing WR without sacrificing performance. This fact has several surprising consequences, including that array geometries with identical co-arrays and physical sensor counts can have different identifiability properties at reduced WR.

Contributions: This paper establishes that certain redundant arrays cannot reduce waveform rank without sacrificing identifiability. Specifically, we show how the ability to operate at low WR depends on the subspace properties of the redundancy pattern, and that its combinatorial and binary structure renders characterizing these properties highly nontrivial. We then derive a novel necessary condition for maximizing identifiability at reduced WR. This condition pinpoints a general structure in the co-array that hampers identifiability at low WR. Finally, we validate our theoretical findings via illustrative simulations.

Related work: Sparse arrays [12]–[14] and waveform design [15]–[17] have attracted significant research interest, most recently in the context of ISAC [18]–[21]. For example, [19] considered a precoder design problem with rank and identifiability constraints. However, leveraging array redundancy to reduce precoder rank with identifiability guarantees was not explored. We fill this gap by providing new insights into low-rank waveform design and its dependence on the redundancy pattern of the array geometry. Identifiability in multisensor systems has also been widely studied [22]–[26]. For instance, [27] recently revisited the identifiability of (oversampled) ULAs—the canonical redundant array—in passive sensing. Works on active sensing also exist [1], [28]–[31], but typically assume full-rank waveforms or do not provide rigorous identifiability conditions. Our results address this limitation by revealing the

impact of low-rank transmit waveforms on identifiability when employing redundant array geometries, and showing when lossless WR reduction is impossible. Our preliminary work [32] showcased a subset of the ideas developed in this paper by providing an isolated example of arrays failing at reduced WR. This manuscript significantly generalizes [32] and our earlier preprint [33] by deriving a novel necessary condition for redundant arrays to operate at reduced WR. This so-called nonredundant singleton subset (NRS) condition was not identified in [32], [33]. The manuscript also contains multiple numerical examples illustrating the theory, which were not included in [32], [33].

II. SIGNAL MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider a narrowband MIMO active sensing system estimating the unknown direction-of-arrivals (DoAs) $\theta \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]^K$ of K targets in the same delay-Doppler cell. Given N_r Rx sensors and T temporal samples, the received backscatter signal can be modeled as $N_r T \times 1$ vector [34], [35]

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}(\theta)\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}, \text{ where } \mathbf{B}(\theta) \triangleq (\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_t}(\theta)) \odot \mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_r}(\theta). \quad (1)$$

Here, $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{C}^{T \times N_t}$ is a known *spatio-temporal Tx waveform matrix*, N_t is the number of Tx sensors, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^K$ are the target scattering coefficients, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}$ a noise vector, and \odot denotes the Khatri-Rao (columnwise Kronecker) product. Moreover, $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_t}(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times K}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_r}(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times K}$ are the Tx and Rx array manifolds, respectively. Under standard ideal sensor assumptions, the (n, k) th element of manifold matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}}(\theta)$ of array $\mathbb{D} = \{d[n]\}_{n=1}^N$ (sensor positions are assumed normalized to units of half a wavelength) can be written as

$$[\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}}(\theta)]_{n,k} = \exp(j\pi d[n] \sin \theta_k). \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) enables decomposing $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ in (1), henceforth referred to as the *spatio-temporal sensing matrix*, as follows [33]:

$$\mathbf{B}(\theta) = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\theta), \text{ where } \mathbf{W} \triangleq (\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}_{N_r})\Upsilon. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_\Sigma \times K}$ is the manifold of the *sum co-array* \mathbb{D}_Σ , defined as the sum set of Tx and Rx sensor position pairs:

$$\mathbb{D}_\Sigma \triangleq \mathbb{D}_t + \mathbb{D}_r = \{d_t + d_r \mid d_t \in \mathbb{D}_t; d_r \in \mathbb{D}_r\}. \quad (4)$$

Matrix \mathbf{W} in (3) is a function of the so-called *redundancy pattern* $\Upsilon \in \{0, 1\}^{N_t N_r \times N_\Sigma}$ [10], which is a binary matrix mapping the unique elements of the sum co-array to the physical Tx-Rx sensor pairs. Section III will return to this key quantity in detail. In the remainder of this paper, we will assume that the sum co-array is *contiguous*, i.e., \mathbb{D}_Σ consists of N_Σ consecutive integers.

Problem formulation: We are interested in the following question: “Can the rank of $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ be maintained at N_Σ (its maximum possible value) for all choices of θ , with a waveform matrix \mathbf{S} of rank less than N_t ?” Indeed, if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) = N_\Sigma$ for all θ ($\theta_k \neq \theta_i, \forall k \neq i$), then it can be shown that up to $K = N_\Sigma/2$ DoAs can be uniquely identified [26].¹ Our goal is to investigate if this can be ensured *even with a waveform matrix with reduced WR*. As we will establish in the next section, the

¹That is, no $\theta' \neq \theta$ can give rise to the same (noiseless) measurement as θ , such that $\mathbf{B}(\theta)\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{B}(\theta')\mathbf{x}'$ for all distinct θ, θ' and nonzero \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}' .

redundancy pattern Υ of the Tx-Rx array geometries plays an important and subtle role in determining if this is possible.

III. ROLE OF REDUNDANCY SUBSPACE IN WAVEFORM RANK REDUCTION

The redundancy pattern matrix Υ encodes which of the $N_t N_r$ physical Tx-Rx sensor pairs contribute to which of the $N_\Sigma \leq N_t N_r$ unique virtual sensors per the following definition.

Definition 1 (Redundancy pattern). *The (i, ℓ) th entry of redundancy pattern matrix $\Upsilon \in \{0, 1\}^{N_t N_r \times N_\Sigma}$ is defined as*

$$\Upsilon_{i,\ell} \triangleq \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } d_t[n] + d_r[m] = d_\Sigma[\ell] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $i = i[n, m] \triangleq m + (n - 1)N_r$. That is, $\Upsilon_{i,\ell}$ is unity if Tx-Rx pair i contributes to virtual sensor ℓ (zero otherwise).

The columns of Υ encode the redundancies of the sum co-array elements in \mathbb{D}_Σ (which is a set with nonrepeated elements). For a nonredundant array ($N_t N_r = N_\Sigma$), Υ is a (square) permutation matrix, since, by definition, each column (in addition to each row) contains only one nonzero entry. In this case, full WR is necessary to maximize identifiability. Indeed, if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t$ and $N_\Sigma = N_t N_r$, then $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) \leq \text{rank}(\mathbf{W}) \leq \text{rank}(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}_{N_r}) = \text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) \text{rank}(\mathbf{I}_{N_r}) < N_t N_r = N_\Sigma$. This establishes that for nonredundant arrays, it is impossible to reduce WR while maintaining $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) = N_\Sigma$. Therefore, a *necessary* condition for WR reduction is that the sum co-array be redundant ($N_\Sigma < N_t N_r$). But is this sufficient? Section III-A will show that, interestingly, the answer is *no*. To understand why, we first establish that the *subspace* spanned by the columns of Υ controls if a redundant array can achieve maximum identifiability at reduced WR.

Lemma 1 (Redundancy subspace condition). *Given a contiguous sum co-array with redundancy pattern Υ , one can ensure $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) = N_\Sigma$ for all θ using a rank-deficient waveform matrix \mathbf{S} ($\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t$) if and only if $\text{rank}((\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\Upsilon) = N_\Sigma$, i.e., if and only if*

$$\dim(\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}) \cap \mathcal{R}(\Upsilon)) = 0. \quad (6)$$

We refer to (6) as the “*redundancy subspace condition (RSC)*”.

Proof. We introduce the notion of Kruskal rank [36], which enables writing $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) = N_\Sigma$ for all θ equivalently (and compactly) as $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = N_\Sigma$. Here, $\mathbb{B} \subseteq \mathbb{C}^{N_\Sigma \times T}$ denotes the set of possible columns of $\mathbf{B}(\cdot)$ in (3):

$$\mathbb{B} \triangleq \{\mathbf{B}(\phi) \mid \phi \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]\}. \quad (7)$$

The Kruskal rank of \mathbb{B} , denoted $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B})$, is the largest integer ℓ , such that *any* subset of ℓ *unique* elements of \mathbb{B} are linearly independent. Any K angles $\theta \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]^K$ are identifiable if and only if $K \leq \frac{1}{2} \text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B})$ [26, Theorem 11.1]. Showing that $\text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) = N_\Sigma$ for all θ ($\theta_k \neq \theta_i, \forall k \neq i$) is therefore equivalent to establishing that $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = N_\Sigma$.

Before specializing our result to the case of contiguous sum co-arrays, we prove the following generalization of Lemma 1:

$$\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = N_\Sigma \iff \begin{cases} \text{rank}((\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\Upsilon) = N_\Sigma \\ \text{k-rank}(\mathbb{A}_\Sigma) = N_\Sigma. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here, $\mathbb{A}_\Sigma \triangleq \{\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\phi) \mid \phi \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}^{N_\Sigma}$ denotes the set of possible columns of co-array manifold matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\cdot)$ in (3). By (3), $\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, where $\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$. By definition, the Kruskal rank is invariant to linear transforms that preserve the null space. That is, if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{W}) = N_\Sigma$ and $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{A}_\Sigma) = N_\Sigma$, then $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = \text{k-rank}(\mathbb{A}_\Sigma) = N_\Sigma$.

Conversely, suppose $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = N_\Sigma$. Then $N_\Sigma = \text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) \leq \text{rank}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \leq \text{rank}(\mathbf{W}) \leq N_\Sigma$. Hence, all inequalities should hold with equality, i.e., $\text{rank}(\mathbf{W}) = N_\Sigma$. Since \mathbf{W} preserves the null space of $\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, it must hold that $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = \text{k-rank}(\mathbb{A}_\Sigma) = N_\Sigma$, proving (8).

Finally, when the co-array is contiguous², it is well known that $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{A}_\Sigma) = N_\Sigma$, since $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbb{D}_\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is a Vandermonde matrix with distinct columns [38, p. 345]. Hence, if \mathbb{D}_Σ is contiguous, then $\text{k-rank}(\mathbb{B}) = N_\Sigma$ if and only if $\text{rank}((\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = N_\Sigma$. Eq. (6) then follows from the rank-nullity theorem:

$$\text{rank}((\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = \text{rank}(\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) - \dim(\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}) \cap \mathcal{R}(\boldsymbol{\Upsilon})),$$

since $\text{rank}((\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = N_\Sigma = \text{rank}(\boldsymbol{\Upsilon})$ by definition. \square

Remark 1 (Challenges in satisfying RSC). *Lemma 1 implies that a redundant sum co-array is not enough for WR reduction—rather, the exact redundancy pattern $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ matters. In other words, $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ has to permit the existence of reduced rank \mathbf{S} satisfying RSC. Determining this is highly nontrivial, mainly due to the specialized combinatorial and binary structure of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$, which limits possible choices of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ and thereby its column space. Similarly, Kronecker structure $\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}$ makes it nontrivial to characterize rank-deficient \mathbf{S} satisfying (6) given $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$.*

When both \mathbf{S} and $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ are given, the RSC simply reduces to checking the rank of a known matrix. Remark 1 is most strikingly illustrated by the fact that for certain redundancy patterns $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$, no rank-deficient waveform matrix \mathbf{S} exists such that (6) holds, as the next section shows.

A. Necessary condition for redundancy subspace condition

The problem of which redundancy patterns $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ satisfy (6) when \mathbf{S} is rank deficient is currently wide open. As a step towards bridging this gap, we show the existence of a certain set of columns in $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ violates (6) for any rank-deficient \mathbf{S} .

Definition 2 (Nonredundant singleton subset). *A subset \mathbb{S}_{NRS} of \mathbb{D}_Σ is called a nonredundant singleton subset (NRS) if it satisfies the following properties:*

- 1) $|\mathbb{S}_{\text{NRS}}| = N_t$.
- 2) *The redundancy of each element of \mathbb{S}_{NRS} is 1.*
- 3) *Each element of \mathbb{S}_{NRS} can be expressed as the sum of the same Rx sensor with one of the N_t Tx sensors.*

That is, an NRS is a set of virtual sensors formed by pairing all Tx sensors with one Rx sensor, where none of the resulting virtual sensors overlap with those of other Tx-Rx pairs.

Property 2 of Definition 2 simply means that the columns of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ corresponding to co-array elements \mathbb{S}_{NRS} have a single

²In the noncontiguous case, the RSC (6) remains necessary, but not sufficient. Identifiability conditions are more challenging to derive for the noncontiguous case (cf. [37]), which is hence left for future work.

nonzero entry each. This can be expressed using the multiplicity $v(d_\Sigma)$ of co-array element d_Σ as $v(s) = 1, \forall s \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{NRS}}$, where $v(d_\Sigma) \triangleq \sum_{d_t \in \mathbb{D}_t} \sum_{d_r \in \mathbb{D}_r} \mathbb{1}(d_t + d_r = d_\Sigma)$. Moreover, by Property 3, each element $s \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{NRS}}$ can be written as $s = d_t + d_r'$ for some Rx sensor $d_r' \in \mathbb{D}_r$, fixed for all $s \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{NRS}}$, and Tx sensor $d_t \in \mathbb{D}_t$ depending on s .

The following theorem proves that for RSC to be satisfied, it is necessary that \mathbb{D}_Σ does not contain an NRS.

Theorem 1. *If sum co-array \mathbb{D}_Σ contains an NRS, then no choice of rank-deficient \mathbf{S} can satisfy RSC (6). In other words, RSC holds only if \mathbb{D}_Σ does not contain an NRS.*

Proof. We prove that the existence of an NRS implies that redundancy subspace condition (6) is violated for all rank-deficient \mathbf{S} . For convenience, let \mathbb{I}_ℓ denote the set of Tx-Rx sensor indices contributing to the ℓ th virtual sensor:

$$\mathbb{I}_\ell \triangleq \{(n, m) \text{ such that } d_t[n] + d_r[m] = d_\Sigma[\ell]\}. \quad (9)$$

Hence, if $(n, m) \in \mathbb{I}_\ell$, then the ℓ th column of redundancy pattern matrix $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ has a nonzero entry on row $i = m + (n-1)N_r$, by Definition 1. This indexing allows equivalently expressing the ℓ th column of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ using a sum of Kronecker product:

$$[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, \ell} = \sum_{(n, m) \in \mathbb{I}_\ell} \mathbf{e}_n^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_p^P \in \{0, 1\}^P$ is the standard unit vector (of length P) whose p th entry is unity. Furthermore, let $\mathbb{J} = \mathbb{S}_{\text{NRS}} + 1$ denote the virtual sensor indices of NRS elements \mathbb{S}_{NRS} . This follows from the contiguity of the sum co-array, as the virtual sensors can be indexed as $d_\Sigma[\ell] = \ell - 1, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, N_\Sigma$ without loss of generality. By Property 1 of Definition 2, we may write $\mathbb{J} = \{i_n\}_{n=1}^{N_t}$. By Property 2, \mathbb{I}_i is a singleton when $i \in \mathbb{J}$, i.e., $|\mathbb{I}_i| = 1, \forall i \in \mathbb{J}$. Hence, column $i_n \in \mathbb{J}$ of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ satisfies

$$[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, i_n} = \sum_{(n', m') \in \mathbb{I}_{i_n}} \mathbf{e}_{n'}^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_{m'}^{N_r} = \mathbf{e}_n^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r},$$

where Rx sensor index m is fixed for all $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_t$ by Property 3. Hence, the submatrix of $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ formed by columns \mathbb{J} (corresponding to the NRS elements \mathbb{S}_{NRS}) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} [\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, \mathbb{J}} &\triangleq [[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, i_1} \quad [\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, i_2} \quad \dots \quad [\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, i_{N_t}}] \\ &= [\mathbf{e}_1^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r} \quad \mathbf{e}_2^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{e}_{N_t}^{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}] \\ &= \mathbf{I}_{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the corresponding columns of $(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}_{N_r})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ become

$$(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}_{N_r})[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, \mathbb{J}} = (\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I}_{N_r})(\mathbf{I}_{N_t} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}) = \mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}.$$

These N_t columns are linearly dependent when \mathbf{S} is rank deficient. That is, if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t$, then, clearly,

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}) = \text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) \text{rank}(\mathbf{e}_m^{N_r}) = \text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) < N_t.$$

Hence, $(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$, which contains the set of linearly dependent columns $(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}]_{:, \mathbb{J}}$, is also column rank deficient. Thereby RSC (6) is violated and the proof is completed. \square

A few remarks are in order. Firstly, while the absence of an NRS is necessary for satisfying RSC (per Theorem 1), it is currently unknown whether it is also sufficient. Secondly, if

an NRS does not exist, it is still nontrivial to prove that RSC is satisfied (and if so, for which choices of rank-deficient \mathbf{S}). Thirdly, finding all array geometries that both have an NRS and a contiguous sum co-array is an inherently combinatorial problem, with no known efficient solution. However, to partially bridge this gap, we will now derive one family of such arrays.

B. A family of arrays with nonredundant singleton subset

Define the so-called Generalized MIMO array (GMA) as

$$\mathbb{D}_t = \{0, \Delta, \dots, (N_t - 1)\Delta\}, \quad \mathbb{D}_r = \{0, 1, \dots, N_r - 1\}. \quad (11)$$

Here, $\Delta \leq N_r$ is a user-defined positive integer. Similar array configurations to (11) have featured in other contexts [39], [40]. However, their ability to operate at reduced WR has not been investigated before. The following corollary provides conditions under which a GMA permits an NRS and therefore fails to satisfy RSC at reduced waveform rank.

Corollary 1 (Array geometry with NRS). *Consider the GMA in (11). If $N_r/2 < \Delta < N_r$, then the sum co-array of the GMA contains a subset $\{\Delta, 2\Delta, \dots, N_t\Delta\} - 1 \subset \mathbb{D}_\Sigma$ that forms an NRS. Hence, no rank-deficient \mathbf{S} can satisfy RSC (6).*

Proof. See supplementary material.

An example of a GMA for $N_t = 7$, $N_r = 6$ and $\Delta = 4$ is

$$\text{Array 1: } \mathbb{D}_t^{(1)} = \{0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24\}; \mathbb{D}_r^{(1)} = \{0, 1, \dots, 5\},$$

which has a contiguous sum co-array with $N_\Sigma = 30$ elements containing NRS $\{3, 7, 11, 15, 19, 23, 27\}$. While Corollary 1 specifies a family of array geometries that do not permit reduction in WR, one can also find arrays with favorable redundancy patterns that satisfy RSC. Such an example is

$$\text{Array 2: } \mathbb{D}_t^{(2)} = \{0, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 24\}; \mathbb{D}_r^{(2)} = \{0, 1, \dots, 5\},$$

with the same sum co-array and number of physical sensors as Array 1. It can be verified that Array 2, is able to satisfy redundancy subspace condition (6) at reduced WR, unlike Array 1, as we will demonstrate numerically in Section IV. For example, by transmitting $N_t - 2$ independent waveforms from Tx sensor subset $\mathbb{D}_t^{(2)} \setminus \{9, 15\}$, one can satisfy RSC. It can also be verified that the sum coarray of Array 2 does not contain an NRS. Similar conclusions hold for the following two arrays (with identical contiguous co-arrays): Array 3: $\mathbb{D}_t^{(3)} = \{0, 1, 2\}$; $\mathbb{D}_r^{(3)} = \{0, 1, 2, 5\}$, and Array 4: $\mathbb{D}_t^{(4)} = \mathbb{D}_t^{(3)}$, $\mathbb{D}_r^{(4)} = \{0, 1, 3, 5\}$. Our prior work [32] showed that when \mathbf{S} is rank-deficient, $(\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{I})\mathbf{Y}$ has linearly dependent columns in case of Array 3 (violating RSC), whereas Array 4 can satisfy RSC. This can be clearly understood via Theorem 1 and the NRS structure identified herein (unavailable in [32]): the sum co-array of Array 3 contains an NRS (namely, $\{5, 6, 7\}$), whereas that of Array 4 does not. While this suggests that absence of NRS might be both necessary and sufficient for satisfying RSC, establishing sufficiency is still an open question and left for future work.

Fig. 1. DoA estimation using low-rank waveforms (in absence of noise). Identifiability is hampered at reduced waveform rank (WR) when the sum co-array contains a nonredundant singleton subset (NRS). Arrays 1 and 2 have identical sum co-arrays and the same number of (physical/virtual) sensors.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Next, we numerically validate the theory derived in Section III. For DoA estimation, we recover the co-array (ULA) measurement via atomic norm minimization [41] by solving

$$\underset{\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_\Sigma}; t \geq 0}{\text{minimize}} \quad \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{z}\|_2^2 + (t + u_1)\tau \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{u}) & \mathbf{z} \\ \mathbf{z}^H & t \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0,$$

and then apply root-MUSIC [42] to Hermitian Toeplitz matrix $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_\Sigma \times N_\Sigma}$ (assuming K to be known)³. Noise is circularly symmetric Gaussian, $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$, and scattering coefficients are i.i.d. on the complex unit circle, $|x_k| = 1/\sqrt{K}, \forall k$. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is defined as $\mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 / \mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{n}\|_2^2 = 1/\sigma^2$, and the transmit power is $\|\mathbf{S}\|_F^2 = 1$. The ground truth DoAs are $\omega_k = \sin \theta_k = -1 + \frac{2k-1}{K} + \varepsilon_k$, where ε_k is i.i.d. and uniformly distributed in $[-\frac{1}{10K}, \frac{1}{10K}]$, $\forall k$.

Fig. 1a shows the (empirical) mean squared error (MSE) of Arrays 1 and 2 for a varying K when using low-rank waveforms ($\text{rank}(\mathbf{S}) = N_t - 2 = 5$). Results are averaged over 10^3 Monte Carlo trials (varying \mathbf{x} and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, no noise) and 10 random constant-modulus (low-rank) waveforms with i.i.d. phases drawn uniformly from $[0, 2\pi]$. Clearly, Array 1 is unable to identify as many targets as Array 2, as corroborated by Fig. 1b, which shows a sample realization for $K = N_\Sigma/2 = 15$. This is consistent with Theorem 1: an NRS hampers identifiability at reduced WR, even for a contiguous sum co-array.

Fig. 2 shows the MSE of the two arrays as a function of SNR for both low-rank and full-rank (orthogonal) omnidirectional waveforms, where the \mathbf{S} satisfies $\mathbf{S}^H \mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{7} \mathbf{I}_7$ and $\mathbf{S}^H \mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{5} \text{diag}([1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1])$, respectively. The number of targets is $K = 15$. In the low WR case, a gap can be seen between Arrays 1 and 2. This gap grows with SNR, providing further numerical evidence of the importance of avoiding NRSs when operating at reduced WR. Interestingly, Array 2 at reduced WR achieves an MSE comparable to Arrays 1 and 2 at full WR. This suggests that even with noise, judicious array and waveform design can reduce WR without performance loss.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper examined how array redundancy and reduced waveform rank (WR) impact identifiability in active sensing.

³Regularization parameter τ is set to the standard deviation of the noise $\tau = \sigma$ (assumed known). When $\sigma = 0$, we constrain $\mathbf{W}\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{y}$ and set $\tau = 1$.

Fig. 2. MSE vs. SNR using low-rank and full-rank waveforms. Sensing performance at reduced WR deteriorates if the sum co-array contains an NRS. However, judicious redundancy pattern design (avoiding NRSs) can enable low WR designs to match the performance of conventional full WR designs.

Reduced WR can lower hardware costs and transmission time, freeing up spatio-temporal resources for ISAC or enabling beamforming without loss of identifiability. We showed that identifiability at low WR critically depends on the redundancy *pattern* linking physical and virtual sensors. Hence, arrays with identical co-arrays can exhibit fundamentally different identifiability properties under reduced WR. We derived a novel necessary condition for maximizing identifiability at low WR, revealing a structure in the sum co-array called NRS limits the performance of certain redundant array geometries. An immediate implication is that array design for reduced WR should avoid NRSs. Our results provide new insights for resource-efficient MIMO system design, motivating future research on redundancy-aware array and waveform design.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Li, P. Stoica, L. Xu, and W. Roberts, "On parameter identifiability of MIMO radar," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 968–971, 2007.
- [2] J. Li, L. Xu, P. Stoica, K. W. Forsythe, and D. W. Bliss, "Range compression and waveform optimization for MIMO radar: A Cramér–Rao bound based study," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 218–232, 2008.
- [3] A. Hassaniien and S. A. Vorobyov, "Transmit energy focusing for DOA estimation in MIMO radar with colocated antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 2669–2682, 2011.
- [4] H. Q. Ngo, G. Interdonato, E. G. Larsson, G. Caire, and J. G. Andrews, "Ultradense cell-free massive MIMO for 6G: Technical overview and open questions," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 112, no. 7, pp. 805–831, 2024.
- [5] B. Paul, A. R. Chiriyath, and D. W. Bliss, "Survey of RF communications and sensing convergence research," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 252–270, 2017.
- [6] F. Liu, C. Masouros, and Y. C. Eldar, *Integrated Sensing and Communications*. Springer Singapore, 2023.
- [7] M. Ahmadi-pour, M. Kobayashi, M. Wigger, and G. Caire, "An information-theoretic approach to joint sensing and communication," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 1124–1146, 2024.
- [8] V. Koivunen, M. F. Keskin, H. Wymeersch, M. Valkama, and N. González-Prelcic, "Multicarrier ISAC: Advances in waveform design, signal processing, and learning under nonidealities," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 17–30, 2024.
- [9] R. T. Hoctor and S. A. Kassam, "The unifying role of the coarray in aperture synthesis for coherent and incoherent imaging," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 78, no. 4, pp. 735–752, Apr 1990.
- [10] R. Rajamäki, S. P. Chepuri, and V. Koivunen, "Hybrid beamforming for active sensing using sparse arrays," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 68, pp. 6402–6417, 2020.
- [11] C.-L. Liu and P. P. Vaidyanathan, "Robustness of difference coarrays of sparse arrays to sensor failures—Part I: A theory motivated by coarray MUSIC," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 3213–3226, 2019.
- [12] M. Wang and A. Nehorai, "Coarrays, MUSIC, and the Cramér–Rao bound," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 65, no. 4, pp. 933–946, Feb 2017.
- [13] P. Sarangi, M. C. Hücumenoğlu, R. Rajamäki, and P. Pal, "Super-resolution with sparse arrays: A non-asymptotic analysis of spatio-temporal trade-offs," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing*, pp. 1–14, 2023.
- [14] M. G. Amin, Ed., *Sparse Arrays for Radar, Sonar, and Communications*. Wiley-IEEE, 2024.
- [15] M. Bell, "Information theory and radar waveform design," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 1578–1597, 1993.
- [16] N. Levanon and E. Mozeson, *Radar Signals*. John Wiley & Sons, 2004.
- [17] H. He, J. Li, and P. Stoica, *Waveform Design for Active Sensing Systems: A Computational Approach*. Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [18] X. Wang, A. Hassaniien, and M. G. Amin, "Dual-function MIMO radar communications system design via sparse array optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 1213–1226, 2019.
- [19] R. P. Sankar and S. P. Chepuri, "Sparse array and precoding design for integrated sensing and communication systems," in *IEEE 13th Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop (SAM)*, 2024.
- [20] I. Van Der Werf, G. Leus, and S. P. Chepuri, "Receiver antenna allocation for joint sensing and communications," in *IEEE 13th Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop (SAM)*, 2024.
- [21] R. Rajamäki and P. Pal, "Sparse array sensor selection in ISAC with identifiability guarantees," in *58th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers*, Pacific Grove, CA, October 2024, pp. 1–5.
- [22] Y. Bresler and A. Macovski, "On the number of signals resolvable by a uniform linear array," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 1361–1375, 1986.
- [23] M. Wax and I. Ziskind, "On unique localization of multiple sources by passive sensor arrays," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 996–1000, 1989.
- [24] A. Nehorai, D. Storer, and P. Stoica, "Direction-of-arrival estimation in applications with multipath and few snapshots," *Circuits, Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 327–342, 1991.
- [25] Y. Abramovich, N. Spencer, and A. Gorokhov, "Resolving manifold ambiguities in direction-of-arrival estimation for nonuniform linear antenna arrays," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 2629–2643, 1999.
- [26] Z. Yang, J. Li, P. Stoica, and L. Xie, "Chapter 11 - sparse methods for direction-of-arrival estimation," in *Academic Press Library in Signal Processing, Volume 7*, R. Chellappa and S. Theodoridis, Eds. Academic Press, 2018, pp. 509–581.
- [27] M. W. T. S. Chowdhury and Y. D. Zhang, "Direction-of-arrival estimation exploiting oversampled uniform linear arrays," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 33, pp. 51–55, 2026.
- [28] H. Wang, G. Liao, Y. Wang, and X. Liu, "On parameter identifiability of MIMO radar with waveform diversity," *Signal Processing*, vol. 91, no. 8, pp. 2057–2063, 2011.
- [29] G. Shulkind, G. W. Wornell, and Y. Kochman, "Direction of arrival estimation in MIMO radar systems with nonlinear reflectors," in *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2016, pp. 3016–3020.
- [30] Z. Hu, J. Peng, K. Luo, and T. Jiang, "Parameter identifiability of space-time MIMO radar," *Digital Signal Processing*, vol. 90, pp. 10–17, 2019.
- [31] J. Shi, Z. Yang, and Y. Liu, "On parameter identifiability of diversity-smoothing-based MIMO radar," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 1660–1675, 2022.
- [32] R. Rajamäki and P. Pal, "Importance of array redundancy pattern in active sensing," in *IEEE 9th International Workshop on Computational Advances in Multi-Sensor Adaptive Processing (CAMSAP)*, Dec 2023, pp. 156–160.
- [33] —, "Array-informed waveform design for active sensing: Diversity, redundancy, and identifiability," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.06478>
- [34] I. Bekkerman and J. Tabrikian, "Target detection and localization using MIMO radars and sonars," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 3873–3883, 2006.
- [35] B. Friedlander, "On signal models for MIMO radar," *IEEE Trans. on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 3655–3660, 2012.
- [36] J. B. Kruskal, "Three-way arrays: rank and uniqueness of trilinear decompositions, with application to arithmetic complexity and statistics," *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 95–138, 1977.

- [37] P.-C. Chen and P. P. Vaidyanathan, "Rank properties of manifold matrices of sparse arrays," in *55th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, 2021, pp. 1628–1633.
- [38] P. Stoica and R. L. Moses, *Spectral analysis of signals*. Pearson Prentice Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ, 2005.
- [39] D. W. Bliss, K. W. Forsythe, and C. D. Richmond, "MIMO radar: Joint array and waveform optimization," in *41st Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers*, 2007, pp. 207–211.
- [40] C.-Y. Chen and P. P. Vaidyanathan, "MIMO radar space–time adaptive processing using prolate spheroidal wave functions," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 623–635, 2008.
- [41] B. N. Bhaskar, G. Tang, and B. Recht, "Atomic norm denoising with applications to line spectral estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 61, no. 23, pp. 5987–5999, 2013.
- [42] A. Barabell, "Improving the resolution performance of eigenstructure-based direction-finding algorithms," in *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, vol. 8, 1983, pp. 336–339.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL: PROOF OF COROLLARY 1

We show that if $1 < \frac{N_r}{\Delta} < 2$, then set $\mathbb{S} = \{\Delta - 1, 2\Delta - 1, \dots, N_t\Delta - 1\}$ is an NRS of the GMA (11). First, note that the sum co-array $\mathbb{D}_\Sigma = \mathbb{D}_t + \mathbb{D}_r$ is contiguous by (11) and the fact that $\Delta \leq N_r$. Furthermore, \mathbb{S} is a subset of \mathbb{D}_Σ , i.e., $\mathbb{S} \subseteq \mathbb{D}_\Sigma = \{0, 1, \dots, N_r + (N_t - 1)\Delta\}$, since $\Delta \geq 1$ and $N_r - \Delta \geq 0$. Moreover, $|\mathbb{S}| = N_t$ by construction. Therefore, \mathbb{S} trivially satisfies Property 1 of Definition 2. To show that \mathbb{S} also satisfies Properties 2 and 3, note that for a GMA, $d_t[n] = (n - 1)\Delta$, $d_r[m] = m - 1$ and $d_\Sigma[i] = i - 1$. Recalling (9), the set of Tx-Rx sensor indices contributing to the $p\Delta$ th virtual sensor, where $1 \leq p \leq N_t$, can therefore be written as

$$\mathbb{I}_{p\Delta} = \{(n, m) \in [1, N_t] \times [1, N_r] \text{ s.t. } (n-1)\Delta + m - 1 = p\Delta - 1\}.$$

We now claim that $\mathbb{I}_{p\Delta}$ is a singleton with $m = \Delta, \forall p$, i.e.,

$$\mathbb{I}_{p\Delta} = \{(p, \Delta)\}. \quad (12)$$

This claim can be established using the condition $1 < \frac{N_r}{\Delta} < 2$. Firstly, it is trivial to see that any $(n, m) \in \mathbb{I}_{p\Delta}$ must satisfy $n \leq p$. We now show via contradiction that $\nexists (n, m) \in \mathbb{I}_{p\Delta}$ with $n \leq p-1$. Suppose that for some $n \leq p-1$, $(n, m) \in \mathbb{I}_{p\Delta}$. In that case, we have $(n-1)\Delta + m - 1 = p\Delta - 1 \implies m = (p-n+1)\Delta$. Since $m \leq N_r$, this implies that $\Delta = \frac{m}{p-n+1} \leq \frac{N_r}{p-n+1} \leq \frac{N_r}{2}$. This contradicts the assumption that $\frac{N_r}{\Delta} < 2$. Hence $\mathbb{I}_{p\Delta}$ is of the form (12), implying that \mathbb{S} also satisfies Properties 2 and 3 of Definition 2, and is thus an NRS. ■